

S I N G L E

D3.2 Cells and KET components fabrication - version 2

WP3, T3.1

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Technical references

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Executive summary

This deliverable, D3.2, summarizes the cell and KET fabrication during M1 – M18 and summarizes the planned manufacture and delivery of cells and KETs for the M19-M32 period. The parts have been and will be manufactured in WP3, Task 3.1, and distributed to tasks in WP1 and WP3. The shipments are made in batches within the tasks to accommodate improvements achieved in parallel tracks. The duration of T3.1 is until M30, and the deliverable is re-occurring, with this last version (D3.2) submitted in M18.

DOCUMENT HISTORY:

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1. Introduction

Electrochemical cells and KETs (Key Enabling Technology components) (Figure 1:) will be fabricated in WP3 under T3.1 and distributed to other Work Packages/Tasks. A list of components that will be fabricated in WP3 is given in Table 1.

Figure 1: Stack reactor shell (left) and multi-cell stack (right) parts. New design has 8 barrels with shorter segments, otherwise the same as the illustration.

Table 1: Overview of new generation delivered in WP3.

Part	Material	Manufacture site
Membrane cell (Ni-BZCY cell)	Ni – BaZr _{0.7} Ce _{0.2} Y _{0.1} O _{3-δ} support BaZr _{0.8} Ce _{0.1} Y _{0.1} O _{3-δ} electrolyte Ni – BaZr _{0.7} Ce _{0.2} Y _{0.1} O _{3-δ} electrode	CTMS in-house
Face seals	GC654 + alumina	Powders and firing by CTMS Outsourced shaping
Gasket seal	GC654	Powders and firing by CTMS Outsourced machining
Interconnect/ bottom manifold	Ni – GC594	GC powders, mixing and firing by CTMS Outsourced machining
Conductive washers	Ni – GC657	GC powders, mixing and firing by CTMS Outsourced shaping

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Table 2: Components distribution from WP3

WP	Task	Type of component to test
1 – Catalytic membrane reactor optimization	1.1 – Improved catalytic activity of Ni-BZCY support	Ni-BZCY cells
	1.2 – Improved stability of Ni-BZCY support under ammonia cracking	Ni-BZCY cells
	1.3. Component compatibility with ammonia	Ni-BZCY cells Glass ceramic seals Interconnects
	1.4 Testing optimized single cells	Reference Ni-BZCY cells Optimized Ni-BZCY cells
3 – Fabrication and validation of catalytic membrane stacks	3.2 – Stack manufacturing	Reference stack Improved stacks
	3.4 – Validation of stack components	Reference stack Improved stacks

The improvement activities in tasks 1.1 and 1.2 have so far not shown a requirement to re-match the thermal expansion of components. A new generation of membrane cells however have a higher TEC and sealing materials have been adjusted to accommodate this.

D3.2 outlines the manufacturing schedule for T3.1 and distribution of parts to other tasks and WPs. The components manufactured in the task will serve the improvement activities in WP1 in a way that coordinates with the other manufacture activities in WP3 (T3.2 and T3.4).

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2. Activities in related tasks

Components are distributed to several tasks within two work packages, as such, improvement tracks will run in parallel. Components will therefore be shipped in batches to ensure that improvements are developed based on updated components from parallel tracks. The number of parts to be shipped is based on the planned experimental test matrixes from the improvement tasks.

2.1. Improvement tracks in WP1

T1.1 led by CSIC, has been provided Ni-BZCY half cells to:

- CSIC for infiltration with a selection of metals to increase activity for ammonia dehydrogenation (ADH) reaction.
- CTMS to pursue the galvanic replacement route to introduce Fe and Ru in the structure to increase the catalytic activity.

In M6, two batches of Ni-BZCY of G21 cells were shipped to CSIC and CTMS for pre-screening activities. At CSIC, cells have been infiltrated with a selection of metals, crushed and sieved into powder and tested in a fixed bed reactor for ADH. The improvement tracks were carried out in 3 iterations:

- Initial screening of performance for selection of infiltrated metals and metal loadings (partially done at CSIC)
- Screening of performance for the most promising metals and metal loadings with optimized conditions
- Performance of cells infiltrated with most promising metals and with microstructure optimized for stability in T1.2

In M17 a batch of Ni-BZCY cells of G23 have been shipped to CSIC for infiltration.

T1.2 led by CTMS, has been provided with Ni-BCZY cells of various microstructure to CTMS to investigate the effect of microstructure during long-term performance during ADH operation. Furthermore, also Ni-BCZY3 cells, a new variant of BCZY with more Ce in the structure, are provided to test the stability under ADH. In M6, two batches of cells have been delivered to CTMS for screening activities. The further improvement tracks were carried out in 2 iterations:

- Initial screening of cell stability related to microstructure

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- Screening of cell stability with optimized microstructure and metal infiltration

T1.3 is led by CSIC. Sealed barrels as well as individual components such as Ni-BCZY cells, cell materials, glass seals and interconnects has been delivered by CTMS to this task. Components have been used to investigate the compatibility with ammonia and under ADH conditions. In M6 two batches of G21 was sent for this task. The list of components can be found in Table 3 under WP1 T1.3.

- Reference components (M2)
- Adjusted components for G23 cells (M17)

In M17, a batch of G23 Ni-BZCY cells have been shipped off to CSIC to benchmark new cells under relevant conditions.

T1.4 is led by CSIC. Optimized cells based on the improvements from T1.1 an T1.2 will be assembled and delivered to this task. The cell assembly will be tested for benchmarking the performance under relevant conditions. Performance testing will be carried out in 3 iterations.

- Benchmarking reference cells under relevant conditions
- Cells with improved stability
- Cells with improved stability and performance

In M6 a batch of three sealed single cell assembly with pre-existing design was sent to CSIC for performance testing under relevant conditions.

2.2. Manufacture and validation activities in WP3

T3.2 is led by CTMS and components will be delivered to the task for stack assembly. Currently one stack has been produced and delivered in M6, based on pre-existing CTMS design and used to establish a baseline in performance in T3.5. Fabrication of subsequent SEUs has been put on a delay to include new improvements. These improvements comprise mainly of new cell generation, denoted G23, and at a later stage also new steel header material. A next shipment of 2 stack with G23 cells will be sent to CSIC for pilot plant commissioning. A third and fourth shipment will be sent to CSIC to reach the nominal 10 kg/day of H₂.

T3.4 is led by CTMS and components has been delivered to the task for performance validations. Parameters that has been validated include thermomechanical properties, electrochemical properties and the DC conductivity.

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3. Manufacture plan

3.1. Manufacture methods

Ni-BZCY cells are made on a regular basis at CTMS' facilities. The manufacture procedure comprise the following steps:

- Mixing of ceramic powders with NiO, water and binders into a paste.
- Shaping of the ceramic paste by extrusion with subsequent drying.
- Spray coating the green BZCY-NiO support with BZCY electrolyte.
- Screen printing the BZCY-NiO outer electrode.
- Binder burnout and co-firing the coated green tubes (support electrode, electrolyte, outer electrode).
- Annealing in hydrogen-containing atmosphere to reduce NiO to metallic Ni.

One production cycle requires minimum 3 weeks (including quality control)..

For the stack components, powders are mixed in batches and shaping is mainly outsourced. It is not expected that changes will be made to these parts. The production cycle for a ceramic stack involves multiple overnight sealing cycles, electrical contacting and quality control, and expected time for one production cycle is 2-3 weeks. Welding of the outer reactor housing is done by an external contractor and therefore done batchwise.

3.2. Delivery schedule

The distribution of components to the relevant tasks are listed in Table 3. The components delivered to T1.4 and T3.2 will be used to assemble single tube test samples and ceramic stacks. A surplus of components will be delivered to account for yield losses when necessary. For the improved stacks it is assumed that the yield and design are similar as for the reference stack. This is however subject to change, and numbers given in the table are mainly meant to reflect the number of samples/stacks. The time of shipments are listed in Table 4.

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Table 3: Distribution of components to relevant tasks

WP / Task	Type of component	#parts/shipment			
		1st	2nd	3rd	4th
WP1 / T1.1	Ni-BZCY half cells	40	20	-	-
WP1 / T1.2	Ni-BZCY cells	18		-	-
WP1 / T1.3	Ni-BZCY cells	6	6	-	-
	Interconnect	1 (6pcs)	1 (6pcs)	-	-
	Conductive washer	6	6	-	-
	Glass ceramic face seals	6	6	-	-
	Glass ceramic gasket seals	1 (6pcs)	1 (6pcs)	-	-
	Top manifold	1 (6pcs)	-	-	-
	Sealed barrel section	1 (6pcs)	1 (6pcs)	-	-
WP1 / T1.4	Sealed single tube assembly	3	-	-	-
WP3 / T3.2¹	Ni-BZCY cells	98	96	240	960
	Interconnect	7	14	35	140
	Conductive washer	42	96	240	960
	GC face seals	42	96	240	960
	GC gasket seals	9	14	35	140
	Top manifold	1	2	5	20
	Bottom manifold	2	2	5	20
	Reactor top lid	1	2	5	20
	Reactor bottom lid	1	2	5	20
	Reactor shell	1	2	5	20
WP3 / T3.4	Ni-BZCY cells	6	-	-	-
	Interconnect	1	-	-	-
	Conductive washer	1	-	-	-
	GC face/gasket seal	1	-	-	-
	Steel-to-ceramic transition	1	-	-	-
	Sealed barrel	6	-	-	-

Table 4: Delivery schedule.

¹ Design and yield subject to changes.

WP / Task	Month for shipment			
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th
WP1 / T1.1	M6	M17	-	-
WP1 / T1.2	M2	-	-	-
WP1 / T1.3	M6	M17	-	-
WP1 / T1.4	M8	-	-	-
WP3 / T3.2	M2	M22	M26	M29
WP3 / T3.4	M6		-	-

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